

Fathers and Children: Male Fertility in Russia in the First Quarter of the XXI century

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Abstract

Gender is a mandatory attribute in the study of all demographic processes, except for fertility, which is traditionally measured relative to the female population. In recent decades, interest in research on male fertility has increased significantly, due to a reassessment of their role in the formation and development of the family. The purpose of our article is to draw attention to the study of male fertility in Russia. For this purpose, male fertility was calculated for the period from 2000 to 2023 based on government statistics. It was found that the ratio of total fertility rates for men and women in Russia has changed ambiguously: until 2011, the total fertility rate was higher for men, but then the situation changed in favour of women. This phenomenon, as shown in the article, is explained by the peculiarities of changes in the age composition of the population. The analysis of the dynamics of calculated fertility rates and mean age at birth for men is carried out in an international context. Fathers in Russia are younger than in other countries with low fertility, but this difference is smaller for fathers than for mothers. Moreover, the difference in the average age of parents in Russia is one of the largest in Europe. The study demonstrates that studying male fertility using Russian data is feasible and adds new analytical information to the picture of demographic development.

Keywords

male fertility, total fertility rate, age-specific fertility rates, average age at birth, Rosstat, Russia

JEL codes: J13

Introduction

In demographic analysis, gender, along with age, are the main demographic variables (Bogue 1969; Adjamagbo, Locoh 2014). The probability of occurrence of certain demographic events depends on the age and gender of an individual, and the age-sex structure influences

macrodemographic indicators, such as the total number of demographic events and general demographic coefficients. But if the variable “age” is present in the analysis of all demographic processes, then the variable “gender” has one important exception – fertility. Calculation of demographic indicators and analysis of their differences by gender is an essential component in the study of mortality, marriage and divorce rates, and migration. In practice, widely used are, for example, estimates of life expectancy at birth for men and women, the age at first marriage for men and women, or the intensity of migration in individual age groups for men and women. And only fertility, its characteristics and factors are traditionally studied in relation to the female population. For this reason, the basic theories explaining the evolution and differentiation of fertility, primarily the theory of demographic transition and the concept of intermediate determinants of fertility, are built on the basis of studying fertility in women (Zhang 2011). Classical models of population reproduction and demographic forecasts are also based on the fertility rates of the female population.

The established research tradition is partly explained by the peculiarities of collecting and developing demographic data. As the famous Soviet demographer L.E. Darsky wrote, the use of female indicators has developed traditionally and is due to more complete statistical data on female age-specific fertility (Darsky 1972). This state of affairs, both in statistics and in the analysis of fertility, was also facilitated by established gender stereotypes in which motherhood and childhood are inextricably linked, and fathers have no place in this pairing. Men were seen primarily as breadwinners, and their involvement in fertility was limited to fertilization and “creating barriers for women to use contraception” (Greene, Biddlecom 2000: 95). Such discrimination in fertility research has turned men into a neglected minority (Coleman 2000) or into women’s shadow (Bledsoe et al. 2000; Zhang 2011). However, scientists back in the 1970s noted that neither biology, nor the difficulties of counting caused by births out of wedlock, nor the paucity of data were serious reasons for the existing bias in the study of fertility (Brouard 1977). Subsequently, this gender imbalance began to be gradually overcome, which was facilitated by several factors. Among the latter, the following are highlighted: progress in collecting and storing information on demographic events, discovered differences in fertility rates between men and women (Schoumaker 2019), a reassessment of the role of men in the formation and development of families (Greene, Biddlecom 2000), including in making decisions about having a child (Marciano 1979), assessments of the consequences of low fertility (Dudel, Klusener 2016), justification of demographic policies and family planning programmes that should be aimed not only at the female but also at the male population (Demography and family... 2016; Aventin et al. 2023).

Demographic studies of male fertility, or, in other words, male fertility in Russia, are at their very beginning: there are only a few relevant publications. Our article aims to advance this topic in Russian demography. Conventionally, it can be divided into two parts. The first, or “historiographic,” part uses a lengthy review of scientific literature to show how the “male” direction of demographic research on fertility has developed and what its current state is in the world. The second part, based on government statistics, provides estimates of the main indicators of male fertility (age and total rates, average age at birth) from 2000 to 2023 in Russia. Particular attention is paid to the change in the ratio of total fertility rates of men and women and its explanation. The analysis of the dynamics of the calculated indicators is carried out in an international context. In a certain sense, the article expands on the results of V. Arkhangelsky and O. Kalachikova, in which male fertility rates in Russia were estimated for 2011–2019 (Arkhangelsky, Kalachikova 2021).

Male fertility in demographic studies

The first estimates of male fertility appeared in the 1920s and 1930s and were associated with the construction of population reproduction models. The German demographer R. Kuczynski (Kuczynski 1932) was one of the first to calculate age-specific fertility rates and reproduction rates for both sexes using France as an example in 1920–1923. In those years, scientists established the so-called demographic “contradiction” (“conflict”) between the male and female populations. As is known, the classical model of a stable population is built on the basis of fertility rates calculated for the female population. If a model is constructed for the same population based on fertility rates for the male population, then, as a rule, different indicators of the reproduction regime are obtained as a result. Attempts to construct a two-sex model did not lead to stabilization of the age structure.

A little later, an article by K. Tietze was published (Tietze 1938), in which he calculated his proposed age-specific paternity rates for Sweden. In fact, they repeat the calculation of age-specific fertility rates relative to the female population. A remarkable feature of this work is the assessment of these rates for fathers from different professional and social groups (those employed in industry, transport and trade, civil servants, non-agricultural workers, farmers and others).

In the 1930s and 1940s, interest in male fertility was primarily associated with the search for a resolution to the conflict between the male and female populations within the framework of constructing indicators and models of reproduction. These studies included estimates of age-specific and total fertility rates, net and gross reproduction rates for both women and men. Among the authors of such studies were outstanding demographers from different countries: R. Myers (Myers 1941)¹, P. Vincent (Vincent 1946), G. Karmel (Karmel 1947, 1949), J. Hajnal (Hajnal 1950)². G. Carmel’s work is of particular interest because he attempted to resolve the contradiction between male and female populations by incorporating marriage into a model of a stable population. The search for integrated indicators of reproduction that take into account the characteristics of both men and women continues today. For example, in (Keilman et al. 2014) two new indicators are substantiated: the two-sex net reproduction rate and the two-sex total fertility rate.

Until the late 1970s, men were rarely included in demographic studies of fertility³. Over time, particularly since the 1990s, as data became more readily available, the number of publications on male fertility has increased. But it was significantly smaller in quantity than traditional fertility studies. Thus, according to the Poplin information and bibliographic system on population issues, which was in operation in the last century, over 75,000 articles on fertility were published between 1950 and 2000, of which only 381 articles studied fertility in relation to men, and two-thirds of these were devoted to medical and biological problems (Zhang 2011).

1 In Russian-language literature, there is a tradition of bringing up the American demographer Robert Myers. The Myers age accumulation indices are known. Although a more accurate translation of this scientist’s name is Robert Myers.

2 In Russian-language literature, there is a tradition of bringing up the demographer John Hajnal (Hajnal 1979).

3 There are rare examples where male fertility has been measured in studies of family formation. In particular, G. Harter measured the level of male fertility in certain racial, religious and income groups by the average number of children in the family (Harter 1968). Another article examining changes in marital age differences in the United States also provides estimates of the age difference between fathers and mothers (Presser 1975).

The modern stage of demographic study of male fertility, according to our observations, opens with an article by N. Brouard, published in 1977 in the journal *Population* (Brouard 1977). It uses statistical data to estimate age-specific and total fertility rates for the male population of France for hypothetical generations from 1899 to 1974, as well as for real generations (cohorts) born between 1880 and 1930. The results of the comparison of male and female total fertility rates showed that for the hypothetical generations, male fertility was higher than for women up until 1933, and for the real generations – up until the generation born in 1923. The method that N. Brouard used to calculate age coefficients in conditions where the age of their fathers is unknown for some of the new-borns is still used today.

Interest in the problems of male fertility in Germany emerged in the early 1990s. One of the first studies conducted a comparative analysis of the fertility of male and female cohorts born between 1920 and 1960 in West Germany. The information was obtained from a data pool formed from all possible German national surveys in which the sample was random and which contained questions on births to women and men. As a result, taking into account the age difference between spouses of approximately 3 years, it was revealed that in male cohorts born in 1902–1928, the final fertility rate was higher than in women born in 1905–1931. In all cohorts of men born after 1937, fertility was lower than in the corresponding female cohorts (Dinkel, Milenovic 1993). German demographers conducted a separate study that showed how the differences in male fertility rates in West and East Germany have been erasing since 1991. The total fertility rate in the eastern part of the country increased from a low of 0.73 in 1994 to 1.31 births per man in 2013. In western Germany, the TFR increased from 1.26 to 1.36 births per man over the same period. At the same time, the total fertility rate per woman over the same years in East Germany increased from 0.85 to 1.46, and in West Germany, from 1.36 to 1.41 (Dudel, Klüsener 2016).

In the United States, interest in male fertility issues emerged as early as the 1980s. It increased significantly in the following decade, which was facilitated not only by a reassessment of the role of men in the process of family formation and development (Goldscheider, Kaufman 1996), but also by the inclusion of questions on male fertility first in the Current Population Survey and then in other mass national surveys⁴. One of the first publications containing information on the number of children born depending on the year of birth (age), ethnicity, marital status, level of education and income, type of activity, and place of birth, appeared in 1996 (Bachu 1996). Changes in the socio-demographic characteristics of fathers that have occurred since then can be traced using the results of recently conducted representative surveys (Martinez, Daniels 2023). At the same time, the assessment of fertility rates (age and total rates) for men is also carried out based on current US statistics (Dudel, Klüsener 2019a).

Studies of male fertility are also being conducted in other countries. For example, when analyzing statistical data from Greece, it was found that from 1992 to 2011, the TFR in men decreased throughout the period (from 1.4 to 1.15 children per man), and the age curve of paternity shifted to older ages. The decline in male fertility was uneven across educational groups. If in 1992 the highest fertility rate was observed among people with basic education (incomplete secondary), then in 2011 the fertility rate among men with

4 The quality of male fertility survey data in the United States has been the subject of specific studies (See, for example, Mott et al. 2007; Joyner et al. 2012).

higher education was 15% higher than among men with basic education (Tragaki, Bagavos 2014). Data from the Danish population register allowed scientists to calculate the adjusted total fertility rate for both female and male populations using the Bongaarts-Fini method and estimate the rate effects for the period from 1980 to 2010. It was found that in men the tempo effect was less pronounced and was practically not observed at the end of the studied period due to the stabilization of the age of fatherhood (32 years for first births). Female fertility, on the other hand, was characterized by a stronger tempo effect, which persisted in 2010 due to the continuing trend of postponing births (Nordfalk et al. 2015).

The study of changes in the age of fatherhood and its consequences for the health and upbringing of children is a separate area of research. Thus, in the United States, scientists tracked changes in the age of fathers, as well as the difference in the ages of fathers and mothers over the period from 1972 to 2015, taking into account their membership in ethno-racial and educational groups, as well as place of residence (Khandwala et al. 2017). In Finland, a study was conducted using population register data to examine changes in paternal age at first birth depending on social characteristics over the period 1987–2009. It showed that over the specified period this age increased by 1.7 years: from 28.7 to 30.4 (Paavilainen et al. 2016). It was found that the highest age and its greatest increase were observed among residents of Helsinki, holders of master's and doctoral degrees. Concerned about the medical, social, and demographic consequences of aging parenthood, the authors offer a series of recommendations aimed at rejuvenating it. Among them is encouraging parenthood among university students. Male fertility is gradually being included in the analysis of demographic trends in individual countries. For example, demographers have examined the demographic evolution of France from 1946 to 2022, including fertility, through the prism of differences between the male and female populations (Breton et al. 2023).

One of the areas of study of male fertility has been the improvement and application of models previously created to describe the fertility process in the female population. For example, to analyze age-related characteristics of fertility in the male population, the Gompertz relational model was adapted and successfully applied using the example of Sweden, England and Wales, the USA and Brazil in the 1970s (Paget, Timæus 1994). The resulting model proved to be more accurate for countries with low fertility rates (Sweden, England and Wales) and less accurate for populations with a high proportion of out-of-wedlock births (Brazil, where the number of children born out of wedlock reached 20–25%). Particular attention was paid to methods for including data with unknown age and other characteristics of fathers in the analysis (Dudel, Klüsener 2019a).

An important area of fertility research is the study of factors that explain its differentiation between different population groups and changes over time. Of interest are the results of a study conducted using population register data in Norway, which determined the influence of age, marital status and education on the fertility of men living in the country from 1970 to 2006. Childlessness among men was most pronounced among those with less than a complete secondary education, and least among those with a higher education. The generations born in the 1960s had a higher rate of childlessness than the generations born in the 1940s. The conclusion about the prevalence of childlessness depending on the field of study attracts attention. As it turned out, the highest level of childlessness was observed among those who studied humanities and arts (philologists, musicians, actors, etc.). They are followed by representatives of social sciences and journalism. In turn, the lowest level

of childlessness was recorded among teachers, doctors and social workers (Lappegård et al. 2011).

Researchers studying the impact of education on male fertility in Finland in cohorts of the 1940s and 1950s confirmed the links found by their Norwegian colleagues. In the studied cohorts, more educated men had more children (the total fertility rate among people with incomplete secondary education was 1.71 births per man, among people with higher education – 2.06), they became fathers later (the average age at the birth of the first child among people with incomplete secondary education was 26.1 years, among people with higher education – 28.1 years). Moreover, the interval between births of children among men with higher education was shorter than among men without higher education. The fact that highly educated men have more children than their less educated counterparts is largely explained by their higher fertility rates at older ages (after 25 years) and lower likelihood of remaining childless (Nisén et al. 2014).

In conditions of limited time data, comparative cross-country analysis plays an important role in studying male fertility, as it allows us to identify both long-term patterns and the factors that determine these patterns. To conduct such an analysis, the Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research (Rostock, Germany) created a database on male fertility based on current birth registration data for 17 developed countries (Dudel, Klüsener 2019b). The undoubted advantage of this database is that a unified methodology was used to resolve issues related to failure to indicate age or the absence of information about the father. For some countries, the time series of indicators begins in the late 1960s – early 1970s, for most – in the 1980s. Among the results of the study of cross-country differences, it is worth noting: firstly, the differences between countries in the dynamics of male fertility, as well as changes in the ratios between the total rates of men and women; secondly, the difference in the ages of fathers and mothers, as well as the ratio of men and women in the corresponding age cohorts as the main factors of these changes; thirdly, a decrease in the difference in the ages of fathers and mothers due to the more rapid “aging” of motherhood (Dudel et al. 2020; Dudel, Klüsener 2021).

Unlike developed countries, in developing countries the main source of data on male fertility is representative sample surveys. The results of these surveys, especially when repeated over time, can yield interesting results. Thus, using data from the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), a group of researchers from the United States and Germany studied the final fertility of cohorts in eight African countries. The study results showed that fertility in men in some countries was significantly higher than that of women: in some cohorts, the final fertility in men was 2–4 births higher than that of women. Such a gap between fertility is possible when the age of fathers is significantly higher than the age of mothers in a population with a young age structure. Polygamy, which is widespread in African countries, increases the age difference between spouses and, as a result, increases the male fertility rate relative to the female fertility rate. Over time, the difference in both the age of parents and the level of male and female fertility is decreasing. The authors of the study suggested that during the demographic transition, the decline in fertility began earlier among men and occurred at a faster rate than among women (Field et al. 2016).

The patterns that had previously been identified using individual countries or groups of countries as examples, and the hypotheses that explained them, were confirmed by B. Schoumaker based on a generalization of available data on male fertility for 163 countries (Schoumaker 2019). For 86 countries, the main source of information was sample

surveys, for 68 countries – current birth registration data, and for the rest – population censuses. Based on these data, age-specific fertility rates for men, the ratios between the total fertility rates of men and women, and the average age of fatherhood and motherhood were calculated and analyzed. These calculations were preceded by an analysis of approaches to estimates obtained on the basis of sample surveys (Schoumaker 2017). As a result, it was shown that the degree of differentiation in male fertility rates is higher than in female fertility rates. In developing countries, the total fertility rate for men exceeds the rate for women in some cases by a significant amount (one and a half to two times or more). In developed countries, these differences are insignificant and often work in favour of women. The main factors explaining the differences between the sexes in the total coefficients and the dynamics of their ratio are demographic: the difference in the age of parents and the ratio in the size of the corresponding cohorts of fathers and mothers. If at the beginning of the demographic transition the total fertility rate was higher for men, then as it progresses the difference between the levels of male and female fertility decreases and becomes inverse, i.e. the level is higher for women than for men. In general, in the demographic transition, according to B. Schoumaker, two related transitions in fertility should be distinguished: among men and among women. Moreover, for men it begins earlier, and the trajectory of decline in fertility is steeper.

Above are the results of studies published in scientific journal articles. It is also worth noting the monographs that played an important role in both the formation and development of the demographic study of male fertility. Particularly notable is the book “Fertility and the Male Life-Cycle in the Era of Fertility Decline,” published in 2000 based on the results of a seminar on male fertility that took place in 1995 in Mexico (Fertility and the Male... 2000). The book attracted considerable attention because it reconsidered both the traditional female-centered view of fertility and the role of men in having and raising children. The problems of fertility in the monograph are analyzed from the standpoint of interdisciplinary and cross-country approaches. Individual chapters were prepared by anthropologists, demographers, sociologists, and historians. The picture of global changes in male fertility is illustrated by case studies of 11 countries and peoples from Germany to Papua New Guinea. The overview chapter on male fertility in industrialized countries was written by the renowned British demographer and author of the theory of the third demographic transition, David Coleman (Coleman 2000).

It is worth mentioning two more books that at one time helped to draw attention to the topic of male fertility. These are the monograph “Dynamics of Human Reproduction: Biology, Biometry, Demography” (Wood 1994) and the collective monograph “Transitions to Adulthood in Europe” (Corijn, Klijzing 2001). The first of these books addresses the natural and immediate determinants of female and male fertility, while the second analyzes trends and causes of changes in the ages of marriage and childbearing among men and women in ten European countries.

In the monographs listed above, a reassessment of the role of men in the process of family development occupied a central place. The first monograph that focused on the demographic analysis of male fertility was the book “Male Fertility Patterns and Determinants” (Zhang 2011). It provides a detailed analysis of the information sources available worldwide and in the United States in the early 2000s, on the basis of which estimates of age-specific and total fertility rates for men compared to women were made for 43 countries. An analysis of long-term fertility trends was conducted using Taiwan as an example. This analysis also confirmed the pattern according to which the ratio of the total

coefficient of men to the total coefficient of women decreases over time, tends to one, and ultimately turns out to be in favour of women. The monograph presents the results of a study of fertility determinants. In this case, using Taiwan as an example, an analysis was conducted of the dependence of the total fertility rates of conditional generations on such aggregate variables as education, place of residence, family income, and marital status of men. Individual data from the 2002 US National Survey of Family Growth were used to examine the socioeconomic and demographic determinants of fertility by age group. Among the findings, we note that high incomes have a positive effect on fertility in men, as opposed to women.

While the number of male fertility studies in foreign countries is steadily increasing, in Russia they remain rare. The author of the most famous publications based on current accounting data is V.N. Arkhangelsky. His first work on this topic appeared back in 1980, and it was subsequently continued (Arkhangelsky 1980, 1998). A 2021 article by V. Arkhangelsky and O.N. Kalachikova presented calculations of age-specific and total fertility rates, as well as the average age of fathers at birth, depending on marital status for the Russian Federation from 2011 to 2019. It also presented a summary of reproductive behaviour surveys conducted in Russia to determine the difference in the desired and expected number of children between men and women, starting from the 1970s (Arkhangelsky, Kalachikova 2021). It should be noted that the calculations in this article were made without taking into account the results of the 2021 All-Russian Population Census, which is why they differ from the estimates proposed by the authors of this article.

Another source of information on male fertility was the first wave of the socio-demographic survey “Parents and Children, Men and Women in the Family and Society” (RiDMiZh), conducted in Russia in 2004 as part of the international programme “Generation and Gender”⁵. Its results include the distribution of men and women by the number of children born and estimates of the average number of children born per man and per woman at a certain age at the time of the survey (Zakharov et al. 2007). The results of the 2004–2006 surveys, which were conducted within the framework of the same international programme in France, Lithuania, and Russia, formed the information basis for a comparative analysis of first and second births by gender and age cohorts of parents, taking into account their marital status, as well as the reproductive intentions of men and women in these countries (Charton et al. 2010). However, these two works do not contain estimates of fertility for calendar periods - age and total rates, or the average age at birth of children. Such estimates were made by D. Alikh in a special study of fertility in Russia based on the same source – the first wave of the RiDMiZh survey. But the main object of his work is the differences between fertility in men and women in Russia in the cohorts born in 1924–1970, depending on age, the length of intervals between births, and the number of children born (Alich 2007).

In 2022, an article by A.A. Avdeev and I.A. Troitskaya was published, which was rare in its content, data sources, and combination of methods of analysis, from both a demographic and historical perspective. It presents estimates of fertility in men among Moscow merchants in the period 1850–1858. Based on data from registers and population censuses,

5 The Generations and Gender Survey programme was initiated by the Population Division of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe and leading European demographic institutes in 2000.

and using modern methods of demographic analysis, the authors calculated marriage rates for men and women of the merchant class and peasants, as well as their age-specific and total fertility rates (Troitskaya, Avdeev 2022).

Data

The proposed work assessed age-specific and total fertility rates, as well as the average age of the father at birth in Russia for 2000–2023. The information to perform the relevant calculations was obtained from two sources. The first – for the period from 2000 to 2010 – is a depersonalized database of birth certificates registered in Russia. The second – for the period from 2011 to 2023 – is the “R248” form developed annually by Rosstat, in which birth data are presented in a matrix format, the columns of which indicate the father’s age, and the rows indicate the mother’s age, for the Russian Federation and its regions. Data from the above-mentioned sources require preliminary processing before calculating fertility, firstly, due to the significant proportion of births for which the father’s age is not specified. Almost all such cases (98–99%) relate to births that are registered at the request of the mother. According to the Order of the Ministry of Justice of the Russian Federation “On approval of forms for recording civil status acts and the Rules for filling out forms for recording civil status acts”, information about the father in cases of registered marriage or established paternity is entered on the basis of relevant documents, and in the case of registration at the request of the mother, information about the father’s age is not entered into the registry office form (Order of the Ministry... 2018). In 2011, the proportion of births with unknown paternal age was 13.1% of the total number of births. By 2023, it decreased to 10.3%. The problem of unallocated births has existed in the past and persists in many developed countries today due to the practice of registering births out of wedlock. Thus, in Germany and the USA, the share of births undistributed by the father’s age in the 1990s exceeded 20%, while in Denmark it approached 50%. In the mid-2010s, due to changes in accounting procedures, this share in Germany and the United States fell below 8%, and in Denmark to 10%. In modern Sweden, this share is 1% (Dudel, Klüsener 2016, 2019a).

Secondly, data from the depersonalized birth certificate database, for various reasons, is usually incomplete and diverges from Rosstat data. In 2000–2010, discrepancies for different years ranged from 0.2% to 17.4%. In this case, an additional task arises of bringing the data of the depersonalized database into line with the data of Rosstat.

For international comparisons, fertility rates from the Human Fertility Collection (HFC) were used. The collection contains estimates of age-specific and total rates, as well as the average age of the father at birth, for 19 OECD countries. However, the length of the time series of indicators varies across countries. Thus, for Sweden they begin in 1968 and end in 2015, for Japan they begin in 2009 and end in 2016. For most countries, data are presented from the 1980s to 2015. To compare Russian male fertility trends, time series for Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Estonia, and Australia were extended to 2023 using data published by the national statistical offices of these countries.

It should be noted that the publication of male fertility data in international publications began three-quarters of a century ago. The second consecutive UN Demographic Yearbook for 1949–1950 published age-specific male fertility rates for 11 countries, calculated using national birth registration data (UN 1950). Subsequently, the range of countries for which

data on male fertility was provided expanded and by the end of the 2010s reached 70. The UN Demographic Yearbook 2012 published estimates of age-specific fertility rates for men in the Russian Federation for 2011 (UN 2012). In the USSR, data on male fertility were calculated for individual years. For example, the State Archive of Economics (RGAE) stores age distributions of births by the age of fathers for the union republics and their territorial-administrative entities for 1958–1960 (RGAE 1958, 1959, 1960). Thus, in Russia there is an opportunity to study patterns of changes in male fertility over a long historical period at a territorial level.

Methods

The main difficulty in calculating male fertility rates, as opposed to female fertility rates, is related, as noted above, to the large proportion of births for which there is no information about the father. There are several approaches to distributing such births by the age of the father. In their study, V.N. Arkhangelsky and O.N. Kalachikova focused on births registered at the request of the mother, since they account for the overwhelming majority of cases where the father's age was not specified. In their opinion, there is no clearly most acceptable basis for distributing births registered at the mother's request by the father's age. The most acceptable would be a conditionally accepted distribution, the same as for those born in this registration category, for whom the father's age is indicated. However, this approach raises doubts due to the small proportion of fathers in this category for whom age is known – only 2-4%. As a result, the authors assessed the distribution of births registered by the mother's application by the father's age (for those for whom it was not indicated) in proportion to the distribution of births registered by the joint application of the parents (Arkhangelsky, Kalachikova 2021).

In this study, births with unspecified paternal age were distributed using a method that has been used in many studies of male fertility, as well as in the creation of the Human Fertility Collection (Brouard 1977; Carmichael 2013; Dudel, Klüsener 2016, 2019). It is based on the assumption that there is a close relationship between the age of the mother and father. In fact, we are talking about a conditional frequency distribution, according to which each age of the mother at the birth of the child corresponds to a certain age distribution of fathers. Next, those born with an unspecified paternal age are distributed among age groups according to this distribution, which is determined by the available data on those born with a specified paternal age. Formally, the calculation of the adjusted value of the number of births $B(i, j)$ at the age of father i and mother j can be written as follows:

$$B(i, j) = B'(i, j) + \frac{B'(i, j)}{\sum_i B'(i, j)} \cdot B(\text{unkn}, j),$$

where

$B'(i, j)$ is the known number of children born to a father at age i and a mother at age j ,

$B(\text{unkn}, j)$ – number of children born to mother at age j , father's age unknown,

$\sum_i B'(i, j)$ – the total number of births in a mother aged j with a known age of the father.

At the same time, the statistical forms include births for whom the mother's age is unknown, as well as births for whom the age of both parents is unknown. Therefore, an additional task is to distribute such observations by age. The distribution of mothers with unknown age (there are few of them in Russia, in 2023 – less than 0.03% of all births) is carried out using procedures similar to the distribution of fathers with unknown age. The distribu-

tion of births with unknown ages of both parents is carried out on the basis of a matrix, the columns of which contain the ages of fathers, the rows contain the ages of mothers, and the cells contain the proportions of births from the total number of births for which the ages of the parents have been established.

As a result of all the above-mentioned procedures, the numerator in the formula for calculating age-specific fertility rates for the male population was determined – the number of births to men of a given age. Next, using known formulas, the total fertility rates of the male population and the average age of the father at the birth of a child were calculated. The upper age limit in the calculations was set at 60 years. The share of births at the ages of 60 and older among men in Russia in the total number of births did not exceed 0.1%. This age limit has been established in many foreign studies and male fertility databases. The fertility indicators for the female population used for comparison were taken from statistical reports of Rosstat.

Differences in fertility rates between men and women

According to the estimates obtained, in 2000 the total fertility rates for women and men were approximately equal (Table 1). In the following decade, they increased, but slightly faster among men than among women. As a result, up until 2011 TFR in men was slightly higher than in women. After 2011, the total coefficient continued to increase until 2015, when it reached its maximum values. But its values in women became higher than in men. Subsequently, fertility began to decline, but the difference between the TFR values increased in favour of the female population. Overall, these differences reached their greatest values in 2020–2023: 0.10 births per parent. But they were not as significant as in some European countries, such as the Netherlands, Germany, Estonia and Sweden⁶.

It should be noted that, unlike Russia, in all the above-mentioned countries the TFR was higher for women than for men throughout the first quarter of the 21st century (Figure 1). Overall, the total rates for men and women changed in the same direction in all countries. But the difference between them in Germany and the Netherlands decreased, and then, from the second half of the 2010s, increased again in favour of women along with the decline in fertility. In Estonia, this difference has steadily increased. In Sweden, the TFR for women was higher than for men, and the difference between them fluctuated around 0.15. If in 2000 Russia occupied the last place in terms of both female and male fertility among the countries named, but in 2023 the TFR of women in Russia was higher than in Germany and Estonia, and the TFR of men was the second highest, behind only the Swedish figure by 0.1 (Table 2).

The average age of fathers and mothers at the birth of a child in Russia, as in all the countries presented in Figure 2, is gradually moving to older ages. In 2000, the average age of fathers in Russia was 28.6 years, and mothers – 25.8 years. By 2023, the average age at birth for fathers increased by 3.6 years, and for mothers by 3.2 years. The smallest changes in the average age of parents were observed in Australia and the Netherlands, where the father's age at birth increased by only 1.6 years (from 32.2 to 33.8 years and from

6 For international comparisons, countries were selected in which the time series of male fertility indicators contained in the Human Fertility Collection – total fertility rates and/or the average age of the father at birth – could be supplemented with new data published in open national statistical sources for the late 2010s to early 2020s.

32.6 to 34.2 years, respectively), and the mother's age increased by 1.5 years in the Netherlands (from 30.3 to 31.8 years) and 2.1 years in Australia (from 29.8 to 31.9 years). The difference between the average age of fathers and mothers in Russia increased until the mid-2000s. In recent years, there has been a tendency towards its decline. In 2023, the average age of parents in Russia was the youngest among the countries considered. Moreover, the difference between the average age of the father and mother was one of the largest – 3.2 years. This difference was greater in Italy (3.6 years), while in Australia it did not exceed two years (Table 2). It should be noted that the age difference between parents from Russia, compared to parents from other countries, was greater for mothers than for fathers.

Table 1. Differences in total fertility rates and mean age at birth for men and women in Russia, 2000–2023

Year	Total fertility rate (per person)		Difference between men and women	Average age at the birth of a child (years)		Difference between men and women (years)
	Men	Women		Men	Women	
2000	1.19	1.20	-0.01	28.6	25.8	2.8
2001	1.23	1.22	0.01	28.8	25.9	2.9
2002	1.31	1.29	0.02	29.0	26.1	2.9
2003	1.38	1.32	0.06	29.2	26.3	2.9
2004	1.39	1.34	0.05	29.5	26.4	3.1
2005	1.35	1.29	0.06	29.8	26.5	3.3
2006	1.37	1.3	0.07	30.0	26.6	3.4
2007	1.47	1.42	0.05	30.3	27.0	3.3
2008	1.54	1.5	0.04	30.6	27.2	3.4
2009	1.57	1.54	0.03	30.8	27.4	3.4
2010	1.60	1.57	0.03	31.1	27.7	3.4
2011	1.60	1.58	0.02	31.2	27.7	3.5
2012	1.68	1.69	-0.01	31.3	27.9	3.4
2013	1.68	1.7	-0.02	31.5	28.0	3.5
2014	1.67	1.74	-0.07	31.6	28.1	3.5
2015	1.70	1.76	-0.06	31.7	28.2	3.5
2016	1.68	1.74	-0.06	31.9	28.4	3.5
2017	1.52	1.6	-0.08	32.0	28.5	3.5
2018	1.47	1.56	-0.09	32.1	28.7	3.4
2019	1.39	1.48	-0.09	32.1	28.7	3.4
2020	1.38	1.47	-0.09	32.2	28.8	3.4
2021	1.37	1.47	-0.10	32.2	28.9	3.3
2022	1.32	1.42	-0.10	32.2	28.9	3.3
2023	1.31	1.41	-0.10	32.2	29.0	3.2

Source: authors' calculations

Figure 1. Dynamics of total fertility rates for female and male populations, Russia, Netherlands, Germany, Estonia, Sweden, 2000–2023 (per capita). *Source:* authors’ estimates for Russia; for other countries – Human Fertility Collection, national statistical agencies.

Table 2. Differences in total fertility rates and mean age at birth of a child for men and women in Russia and other countries, 2022–2023

Country	Last available year	Men	Women	Differences
Total fertility rate				
Germany	2023	1.23	1.39	-0.16
Netherlands	2023	1.29	1.43	-0.14
Russia	2023	1.31	1.41	-0.10
Sweden	2023	1.32	1.45	-0.13
Estonia	2023	1.16	1.31	-0.15
Average age at the birth of a child				
Australia	2023	33.8	31.9	1.9
United Kingdom	2022	33.7	30.9	2.8
Germany	2023	34.7	31.5	3.2
Italy	2023	35.9	32.3	3.6
Netherlands	2023	34.2	31.8	2.4
Russia	2023	32.2	29	3.2
Estonia	2023	33.9	31.0	2.9
Finland	2023	34.2	31.9	2.3

Source: authors’ estimates for Russia; for other countries – national statistical agencies.

Figure 2. Median age of father and mother at birth in selected countries, 2000-2023 (years). *Source:* authors' estimates for Russia; for other countries – Human Fertility Collection, national statistical agencies.

Changes in the total rate and mean age at birth reflect changes in the distribution of age-specific fertility rates. In Russia, following other European countries, there is a gradual shift in the age-related fertility curve for both women and men to older ages (Figure 3). Thus, at the beginning of the analyzed period, the contribution of the 20-24 age group to the total fertility rate for men was 29.5%; by 2023, this figure had decreased to 11.3%. At the same time, the contribution to the total coefficient of the age groups 30-34 years and 35 years and older increased: from 21.5% to 27.3%, and from 13.9% to 30.9%, respectively. At the same time, the contribution of the 25-29 age group to fertility changed insignificantly – from 32.8% to 29.6%. Overall, changes in the age pattern of male fertility are similar to changes in the age pattern of female fertility, adjusted for the difference between the ages of fathers and mothers. The exception is the 25-29 age group, whose contribution to the total fertility rate for women, compared to men, increased slightly between 2000 and 2023.

Age characteristics of male fertility in Russia compared to other countries with low fertility are reflected in Figure 4.

In 2015, the modal value of age-specific fertility rates in Russia was recorded at 28 years, while in Sweden it was 31 years, in England and Wales it was 32 years, and in Italy (estimate for 2014) it was 34 years.

Figure 3. Age-specific fertility rates for men and women in Russia, 2000, 2015, 2023, %. *Source:* authors' calculations.

Figure 4. Age-specific male fertility rates, Russia, Sweden, Italy*, England and Wales, 2015, %. *Source:* authors' calculations for Russia, Human Fertility Collection. *Note:* *for Italy, data refers to 2014.

Demographic factors of differences in the dynamics of male and female fertility

As shown above, the dynamics of the total fertility rates of men and women in Russia over the last quarter century have differed. The direction of change was generally the same: until the mid-2010s, the coefficients increased and then decreased. But what is important is that during this period the ratio between the fertility rate in men and women changed: until 2011, the fertility rate in men was higher than that of women, then from 2012 it became lower. Overall, the differences in the total rates seem insignificant: in the 2000s, the maximum gap was 4% (of the male TFR), in 2023 – about 8%, but the very fact of changes in the ratio of male and female fertility is interesting and requires explanation.

To explain the indicated trend in the change in the ratio of total male and female fertility rates, we will use the approach proposed in the work of Dudel and Klüsener, which studied the differences in fertility between men and women in 17 OECD countries (Dudel, Klüsener 2021). The dependent or explanatory variable is the ratio of the total fertility rate of men to the total fertility rate of women. From 2000 to 2010, the value of this indicator in Russia was greater than 1, in 2011 it was equal to 1, and in subsequent years it was less than 1. To explain this phenomenon from a demographic point of view, let us consider two hypothetical constructs. The first assumes that mortality and migration after birth and until the end of the reproductive period are absent or equal for men and women, and that the age of the father is equal to the age of the mother. In this case, if we take into account the sex ratio at birth in Russia (106 boys per 100 girls), the ratio of the total coefficients will be equal to 0.94. The deviation of the actual ratios from the value of 0.94 is explained by the tertiary sex ratio, which is determined by gender differences in mortality or migration.

A comparison of the actual ratio with the first model shows that the excess of the total coefficient of men over the total coefficient of women was due to their increased mortality (Figure 5). As a result of excess mortality among men, their numbers, i.e. the value of the denominator in calculating age-specific coefficients, decreases, and the total coefficient ultimately becomes greater than that of women. Over time, deviations from the model value of 0.94 decrease, which is partly due to both the accelerated decline in mortality among men in the 2010s and the international migration increase, which in young reproductive ages was in favour of men. But the role of these demographic variables – mortality and migration – is an important, but not a determining factor in the context of a strong demographic wave. As is known, the age composition of the population during the period under study underwent dramatic changes. If we take into account the fact that in Russia the father is 2.8-3.5 years older than the mother, and take for comparison the ratio of the number of generations of men and women approximately corresponding to the average age of the father and mother (Table 1), then from the Rosstat data we can see that in 2000 there were 94 men aged 32 for every 29-year-old woman, and in 2023 – almost 140. As a result, all other things being equal, including the hypothetical assumption of an equal number of births in the same age groups, when calculating age coefficients in the first case for 2000, there will be fewer men than women. This results in a higher total fertility rate for men. In the case of 2023, the opposite situation is observed.

The assumption that the number of births to men in each age group is equal to the number of births to women is the basis for calculating the ratio of total fertility rates by sex in the second model. It eliminates the influence of differences in the duration of the reproductive period, in the birth calendar, and in the age of parents on differences in the fertility rate in men and women. A comparison of the dynamics of the actual gender ratio of total coefficients with

the dynamics of the hypothetical ratio specified by the second model shows that they almost completely coincide (Fig. 5). This points to the decisive role of the age structure in changing the ratio of the total coefficients of men and women in Russia. The close relationship between the model and actual ratios of the total indicators of men and women is also confirmed by a simple regression analysis with a high coefficient of determination equal to 0.96 (Fig. 6).

It should be noted that the patterns discovered generally coincide with those observed in Eastern European countries, such as Estonia. This is explained by the common trends in changes in the age composition of the population and minor changes in the difference in the age of parents.

As the estimates obtained above show (Table 1), in Russia the difference in the ages of fathers and mothers increased significantly (from 2.8 to 3.4 years) in the period from 2000 to 2006 (this phenomenon requires further verification and explanation). Subsequently, its value remained stable (about 3.2–3.5 years), and in recent years there has been a tendency for it to decrease. Changes in the ratio of the ages of parents in conventional generations are a signal that the birth calendar is changing. But if a lot of attention is paid to the study of the birth calendar of women in Russia, then practically none is paid to the birth calendar of the male population due to a lack of data (Alich 2007). In general, due to the relative stability of the difference in the average age of parents, the contribution of this factor to the change in the ratio of the total fertility rates of men and women, in contrast to the changes in the age composition, as shown above, is not significant.

Figure 5. Ratio of actual and hypothetical total fertility rate coefficients for men and women, 2000–2023. *Source:* authors’ calculations.

Figure 6. The relationship between model and actual ratios of total fertility rates for men and women.
Source: authors' calculations.

Conclusion

Although the first attempts to calculate age-specific and total fertility rates for men were made as early as the 1920s, and systematic publication of data in the UN Demographic Yearbooks began at the turn of the 1940s and 1950s, genuine interest in the topic emerged only in the 1990s. From this time on, the number of publications on male fertility began to increase rapidly. This shift was facilitated not only by the scientific community's reassessment of the role of men in the formation and development of the family, but also by the realization that a demographic study of fertility will not be complete if fathers are excluded. Today, data on male fertility is included in standard statistical reporting in many countries around the world; it is published in international reference books and included in various databases. In developing countries, sample survey programmes involve estimating male fertility rates. As a result, the research agenda is expanding to include not only measuring and describing trends, but also studying fertility differentiation across social groups and analyzing the factors that determine fertility patterns among men. Unfortunately, such a research agenda is still absent in Russia, and studies are few and far between.

Statistical information collected in the Russian Federation, which exists in the form of depersonalized data from birth certificates and special Rosstat forms, allows us to calculate key fertility indicators for men: age-specific and total rates, the average age of the father at birth, including taking into account the marital status of the parents. However, unlike for women, the procedures for calculating indicators are complicated by the fact that in births registered at the request of the mother, the father's age is not indicated. This situation requires the use of special methods to distribute these "unknown" fathers by age.

The article presented the results of calculations and analyzed the dynamics of total and age-specific fertility rates, as well as the average age at birth of children for the male pop-

ulation of Russia from 2000 to 2023. It was found that the total fertility rates of men and women change in the same direction, but at different rates. The main feature of this dynamic is that if before 2011 the total fertility rates of men were higher than those of women, then the situation changed to the opposite. Moreover, the differences in the magnitude of the coefficients were insignificant: the maximum in the 2000s was 4%, in 2023 – 7%. But the very fact of a change in the ratio between male and female fertility levels is of interest and requires explanation. Ultimately, it was established that the main factor explaining the change in the ratio of total male and female coefficients is the strong fluctuations in the size of individual age groups. Here it should be taken into account that the average age at birth of a child is 2.8–3.5 years higher than the average age of the mother.

As the results of international comparisons show, the dynamics of fertility rates among Russian men fits into the main fertility trends in other countries with low fertility rates. The age-related fertility curve for men, like for women, is shifting toward older ages, but fertility remains relatively young. Between 2000 and 2023, the average age of fathers increased from 28.6 to 32.2 years, and that of mothers from 25.8 to 29 years. Moreover, the difference in the average age of parents in Russia is one of the highest among countries with low fertility. However, the difference between the average age of fathers in Russia and in Europe is smaller than that of mothers.

In the future, studies of male fertility should be extended to the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, in urban and rural areas, taking into account the marital status of the parents. The information collected during birth registration allows us to estimate the age of fathers at the birth of children of different birth orders, meaning that the calendar effect on fertility can be assessed not only for women but also for men. The accuracy of male fertility rate estimates will be significantly improved if information on the father's age is included in the birth registration process based on the mother's application. Research into male fertility will receive increased attention from the scientific community if Rosstat begins publishing data on, for example, the average age of fathers at birth, as statistical agencies in a number of countries do.

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